

***In-silico* Risk Assessment of Cardiac Conduction Abnormality Associated with Transcatheter Aortic Valve Replacement (TAVR) Using an Electro-Mechanically Coupled Beating Heart Model**

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Introduction

Transcatheter aortic valve replacement (TAVR) procedure is a minimally invasive procedure to treat patients with aortic stenosis. TAVR technology has undergone a rapid evolution due to continuous design improvements. However, some post-TAVR complications remain persistent, with cardiac conduction abnormality (CCA) being one of the major ones. It can occur due to mechanical damage sustained by the atrioventricular conduction system located near the inter-leaflet triangle region between the non-coronary and the right-coronary leaflet¹. In his study, we have used an electro-mechanically coupled beating heart model² to develop an in-silico technique to assess CCA risk incorporating the effect of a dynamic beating heart and pre-procedural parameters such as implantation depth and preexisting cardiac asynchrony in the development of post-TAVR CCA.

Figure 1: (a) Electrical and (b) structural living heart model; TAVR device in (c) open and (d) crimped position; TAVR (e) placement, (f) deployment, (g) cardiac preload, (h) ventricular contraction, and (i) recovery following TAVR procedure.

Methods

A self-expandable 26 mm Evolute stent (Medtronic plc, Minneapolis, MN) deployment was simulated (Figure 1) inside an electro-mechanically coupled beating heart model (The SIMULIA Living Heart Model) in 5 patient scenarios including 3 implantation depths (IDs) and 2 preexisting cardiac asynchronies, one being right bundle branch block (RBBB) and the other being left bundle branch block (LBBB). Critical region of interest (ROI)³ was identified and the time zone of cardiac depolarization through the bundle of His was identified as the critical time (CT) (Figure 2). Mechanical factors such as contact force, contact pressure, and contact pressure index (CPI- percentage of ROI surface area subjected to contact pressure with respect to the total surface area of the ROI) were then measured in the ROI during TAVR deployment and 3 cardiac cycles following TAVR to assess the risk of CCA.

Figure 2: (a) The bottom end of the membranous septum (MS) was identified from the coronal view, (b) bottom MS landmarks were mapped on the 3D model, (c) critical ROI was identified, and (g) cardiac depolarization through the bundle of His was measured and identified as the critical time (CT).

Results

The study demonstrated that the cumulative contact pressure, maximum contact force and average CPI during and 3 cardiac cycles following TAVR were notably lower for the aortic deployment (0.018 MPa, 0.45 N, and 0.13 respectively) compared to baseline (0.29 MPa, 2.34 N, and 28.45 respectively) and ventricular deployment (0.52 MPa, 2.19 N, and 36.21 respectively) (Figure 3). Besides, preexisting RBBB case has demonstrated higher cumulative contact pressure and average CPI during and 3 cardiac cycles following TAVR (0.34 MPa, and 30.82 respectively) compared to the baseline and preexisting LBBB case (0.25 MPa, and 26.62 respectively) (Figure 3).

Figure 3: (a) Total contact pressure exerted on the ROI, (b) maximum contact pressure during CT of 3 cycles, (c) maximum contact force during 2nd and 3rd cycles, and (d) time average CPI for 5 patient scenarios.

Discussion

The results demonstrated that the TAVR implantation above the active contraction zone (ROI) reduces the risk of CCA, and the structural remodeling caused by RBBB increases the mechanical factors causing CCA which explains a strong correlation between preexisting RBBB and post-TAVR CCA reported in several clinical studies.

Conclusions

The novel technique presented here can potentially be used for preprocedural planning and novel TAVR device development to minimize the risk of post-TAVR CCA in a more realistic beating heart condition.

References

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